

ARGULUS

INFECTION

IN FISH

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What is Argulus?

Scientific Classification of Fish Lice

- Kingdom: Animalia
- Phylum: Arthropoda
- Subphylum: Crustacea
- Class: Ichthyostega
- Order: Argulida
- Family: Argulidae
- Genus: Argulus
- Species: *Argulus foliaceus*, *A japonicaus* etc.

Argulus foliaceus are freshwater fish ectoparasites that have been reported in temperate regions of Europe, Central Asia, and North America. It has been well studied in Europe, particularly in the British Isles, and has had a major impact on UK sport fisheries through fish stress and mortality.

Argulus foliaceus occurs in warm, eutrophic, stagnant freshwater and brackish water lakes. Eggs are laid in shady places, not in direct sunlight. Generally considered a shallow water species, this lice is often observed spawning in the upper 1 m of the water column (it will spawn in deeper water at the end of the breeding season). *Argulus foliaceus* is an obligate parasite that can take hosts. These lice have low host specificity, so they can infect a variety of fish in their habitats

Generally, *Argulus foliaceus* has a total length of 3-7 mm and a width of 2.5-5 mm. *Argulus* females are generally larger than males, and the size of the host may influence the development of the parasite. A distinctive feature of *A. foliaceus* is the urosome, which consists of rounded lobes marginally covered with small spines. The posterior incisors of the urosome do not reach the center. Another feature is that the anterior part of the cephalothorax forms a wide protrusion with shallow grooves. Adults use suction cups for host attachment, while larvae use larval hooks.

Argulus foliaceus larvae are free swimming. The length of the larval stage is highly variable, often affected by temperature. Generally, larvae are usually first observed in late spring and mature into adults in autumn. *Argulus foliaceus* is extremely rare in winter. Larval development is divided into two distinct morphological stages: Stage I as a metanoplus and Stage II as a juvenile. While morphological adaptations are seen in stage I larvae, there is currently no firm evidence that stage I is parasitic or pelagic, so they are generally considered "semi-pelagic". Small larvae often hang on the tail end of fish and suck blood.

Morphology

Argulus foliaceus mostly attaches to the host on the skin epithelium of the body and fins, but has also been observed to attach to the gills. These lice feed by piercing the host's skin, injecting a toxin and drawing blood. *A. foliaceus* infection often causes damage to host tissues and sometimes death. *Argulus foliaceus* infects regardless of the health of the host. Host residence time varies slightly between attachment to detachment. Typically, ectoparasites accumulate on the host so that few individuals within the host population are actually infected. Encapsulation may be due to host behavior; When stressed, the host's motility decreases, allowing more parasites to attach.

Argulus foliaceus is an obligate bloodsucker that cannot survive more than a few days without a host. Having little host specificity, it infects a wide range of species.

What causes fish lice?

Fish lice infestations can be caused by a variety of factors, including poor water quality, overfishing, the presence of infected or infested fish, and other environmental conditions that favor parasite survival and reproduction.

Fish that are weakened or stressed due to poor nutrition, disease or other factors are also more susceptible to fish lice infestation.

Fish infected with *Argulus* show symptoms such as inflammation, redness and irritation at the attachment sites, as well as increased mucus production and respiratory distress due to throat infection.

Signs and symptoms of fish lice

- ❖ **Become weak:** The fish has difficulty swimming because it is physically impaired to attack the parasite. At this time, the fish looks thin, weak and sluggish. The fish become unfit for breeding.
- ❖ **Bleeding:** The attacked fish appears to have a small amount of bleeding and a reddish dot from the pelvic fin to the anal fin.
- ❖ **Skin irritation:** It causes skin irritation by increasing the production of mucus on the body surface.
- ❖ **Increased secondary infection:** Skin lesions secondary to infection by bacteria are also seen for the harmful effect of sucking and proboscis.
- ❖ **Anemia and Death:** Secondary infection causes anemia. Small and young fish can die from parasite attacks.

Fish lice treatments

There are two prevention methods for *Argulus foliaceus*. these are:

Manual Treatment: Use hard substrates in pond water to attach *Argulus foliaceus* eggs. Remove it and dry it in the sun to kill the eggs.

Chemical Treatment:

- BHC (Benzene Hexachloride): Bath treatment at .0013-.0017 ppm. But it is toxic to humans and its use is restricted in some countries.
- Pyrethrum: 20-100 ppm for 50 minutes and bath treatment for 10 ppm for 3 minutes.
- Malathion: 0.25-.5 ppm, 3-4 times weekly, and dip in 1% malathion.
- Bytex: Bath treatment at 0.12 ppm is repeated twice at three week intervals.
- Dipterex: Bath treatment at 0.25ppm twice weekly
- Potassium permanganate: 10 ppm concentration for 5 hours.
- Formalin: bath treatment at 250 ppm for 1 hour
- Salt: Bath treatment for 5 to 10 minutes at 2.5-3%.

Disinfection of tanks using Chlorine

References

- Industrial Training in National Aquaculture Development Authority Sri Lanka.
- <https://fisharticle.com/fish-lice-argulus-causes-symptoms-treatment/>